

Mechanistic modelling of solar disinfection (SODIS) kinetics of *Escherichia coli*, enhanced with H₂O₂ – part 1: The dark side of peroxide

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ABSTRACT

The present bi-partite work describes the development and validation of a mechanistic kinetic model of SODIS *E. coli* inactivation, enhanced with H₂O₂. In this first part, the mechanism of the baseline dark phenomena is modelled. A mechanistic model involving *E. coli* cellular respiration, inactivation due to HO[•] and O₂^{-•} radicals, and bacterial thermal inactivation, was developed using a series-event model based on the accumulation of damage and cell recovery corrected with the Arrhenius equation for inclusion of the thermal events. The contribution of external H₂O₂ was included in the internal H₂O₂ balance, while the balance of extracellular H₂O₂ considered the consumption caused by its self-decomposition, interactions with cells' membrane, and organic matter from dead cells. Specifically, the kinetic parameters of the external H₂O₂ sinks, the oxidation reaction of intracellular Fenton, and bacterial thermal inactivation were independently estimated by model regression from experimental data of *E. coli* inactivation and H₂O₂ consumption at different controlled conditions of temperature and initial H₂O₂ concentration. We complemented the values of the kinetic constants available in the literature with the unknown kinetic parameters estimated from experimental and literature data. The missing kinetic parameters were successfully validated (bacteria error = 4.5%, H₂O₂ error = 12.9%). This kinetic model helps to understand the intracellular mechanisms and the contributions of each source of inactivation, with the role of radicals' damage being most important at temperatures below 40 °C, and the thermal inactivation for temperatures above this value.

1. Introduction

The lack of safe drinking water affects more than 700 million people on Earth [1,2]. Among them, most live in low-income countries where the financial and technological resources are limited. Thus, they demand low-cost, sustainable, and user-friendly processes to obtain safe drinking water. These treatments are called Household Water Treatments (HWT) and some examples are chlorination, coagulation-flocculation, boiling, or solar water disinfection. The latter, also called SODIS process, has proven to be one of the most appropriate treatments for producing safe drinking water at household level, because it is inexpensive, not dependent on consumables and has been widely demonstrated to be

effective in removing pathogens from water [3]. This process is based on the germicidal effect of UV light and its synergistic effect with the increase in water temperature. The most widely accepted procedure states that a 2 L polyethylene terephthalate (PET) bottle should be exposed for 6 h on sunny days or 48 h on cloudy days [4]. However, this standard method recommends inaccurate and, sometimes, long disinfection times that could be reduced by changing some features: using materials other than PET that transmit UVB radiation since UVB can directly damage DNA [5], or adding oxidative species, such as persulfate or hydrogen peroxide [6].

The oxidative metabolism is necessary for aerobic respiration in living cells. However, the intracellular presence of oxygen involves the

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formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as superoxide/hydroperoxyl radical ($O_2^{\cdot-}/HO_2^{\cdot}$), hydroxyl radical (HO^{\cdot}), and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), among others. These ROS can attack several cell targets, induce oxidative stress and even lead to cell killing. Oxidative stress has been found to be associated with many pathological, inflammatory, and neurodegenerative diseases such as cancer, Alzheimer's, or Parkinson's disease [7,8]. The formation of ROS is considered a weakness when it is observed in body cells. Nevertheless, aerobic microorganisms also undergo this process, which can be considered as an exploitable vulnerability when applying a disinfection processes. However, being around for millions of years, aerobic microorganisms have developed defence mechanisms to maintain low ROS levels. For example, in *E. coli*, $O_2^{\cdot-}$ can be disproportionated by superoxide dismutase (SOD) enzyme, and H_2O_2 can be neutralised by the alkyl hydroperoxide reductase (Ahp) and catalase (CAT) enzymes, or else it may react with iron producing HO^{\cdot} as a by-product [5]. To put things in perspective, one *E. coli* cell generates about $14 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ internal H_2O_2 when it grows aerobically [9], but the scavenging mechanisms keep the H_2O_2 concentration around 10^{-8} M [10].

During disinfection, when H_2O_2 is present in the aqueous medium surrounding the bacteria, the internal H_2O_2 levels inside rise because H_2O_2 can diffuse into the cell. The permeability of the cell membrane passively controls the H_2O_2 transfer while H_2O_2 is scavenged inside the cell. Thus, the internal concentration may still be an order of magnitude lower than that present outside [10]. In *E. coli*, Ahp is the primary scavenger for concentrations up to 10^{-5} M external concentration [9]. However, at $3\cdot 10^{-5}$ M its activity is saturated, and catalases play the main scavenging role [11]. Generally, H_2O_2 exposure leads to two different inactivation kinetic routes when growing *E. coli* is exposed in a media rich in H_2O_2 [12]. *Mode-one killing* is associated with internal damage produced by radicals' attacks, and it reaches its maximum around 1–2 mM H_2O_2 external concentration. *Mode-two killing* is related to external cell damage, and it prevails for concentrations higher than 10 mM. Between both concentrations, an intervening zone of partial resistance is observed.

It has been previously reported that effective disinfection can be attained by modulating the concentration of ROS in *E. coli* (ergo the intracellular oxidative stress); H_2O_2 concentration can be exacerbated by addition in the pathogens' media or dispersion matrix (e.g. water) when subjected to illumination by UV light [13–17]. This strategy has led to significant inactivation kinetics enhancement as well as regrowth elimination. However, despite its high effectiveness and although the mechanisms that actually drive this synergistic enhancement have seen significant strides [18,19], its true elucidation still escapes to date.

This paper is part of a larger study that aims to elucidate the augmented SODIS inactivation of *Escherichia coli* when enhanced with H_2O_2 . In this first part, only the baseline phenomena occurring in the dark are considered, thus, the oxidative stress induced by adding H_2O_2 is appraised. Nevertheless, since the temperature of the pathogens' media can increase during solar exposure, new routes, independent of the action mode of light may take place. For example, pathogens can be thermally inactivated since high temperatures denature essential proteins [5]. In the case of *E. coli*, its cellular function starts to be interrupted at 40°C due to the melting point of the lipid membranes [20,21]. Besides, the H_2O_2 decomposition rate quickly changes due to its high activation energy ($2884.5 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ H_2O_2 for pure compound or solutions without catalysts) [22,23], which in turn may lead to intensified intracellular oxidative phenomena.

To the best of our knowledge, only one mathematical model has been developed to predict ROS concentrations and explain *mode-one killing* in dark conditions [24]. Despite its rigour and inclusion of various experimental conditions, some key aspects can be further considered, such as the role of $O_2^{\cdot-}$, external H_2O_2 sinks (apart from permeation), or the effect of temperature on the process. The inclusion of these parameters in a new model would significantly increase its mechanistic value, enhance its predicting capabilities and importantly, its potential

coupling with light-induced phenomena.

Under this prism, this Part 1 of the work aims to develop a comprehensive kinetic model that describes *E. coli* inactivation induced by temperature and H_2O_2 addition. A rigorous mechanistic approach is considered, with a view in its expansion to similar illuminated conditions, reducing its complexity, allowing a full SODIS kinetic model enhanced with H_2O_2 . The current approach considers two main radical species involved in the intracellular oxidative stress (HO^{\cdot} and $O_2^{\cdot-}$) and several H_2O_2 sinks, such as thermal decomposition, interaction with the cell membrane and the reaction with organic matter from dead cells. The calibration of the model is performed with different sets of experimental data under controlled conditions, which ultimately validate the predictive capabilities of the model and its suitability to integrate solar light in Part 2 of the work.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and reagents

The chemicals applied in the experiments were all reagent grade or above. The H_2O_2 stock solution in water was prepared with PerdrogenTM (30% w/w H_2O_2 , refrigerated). Plate count agar (PCA), Titanium (IV) Oxysulfate ($TiOSO_4$, 1.9–2.1%) and PerdrogenTM, were all purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Switzerland). The solutions used in this research were prepared prior to experimentation using MilliQ water (18.2 MΩ cm).

2.2. Bacterial strain and growth protocol

The lyophilised pellet of the wild type *E. coli* strain K12 was obtained from "Deutsche Sammlung von Mikroorganismen und Zellkulturen" (DSM Catalogue No. 498). The preparation of the working bacteria stock solution was followed as previously reported [25], obtaining a concentration of 10^9 colony forming units per mL ($\text{CFU}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$). Briefly, a colony from an *E. coli* culture was dispersed in Luria-Bertani broth, and was incubated overnight (greater than 14 h) at 37°C , under constant agitation at 180 rpm, to ensure achieving stationary phase cells with an approximate OD_{600} of 3.5–5.5.

2.3. Inactivation processes

The *E. coli* inactivation processes were carried out in an open vessel, a double-wall reactor with an effective volume of 700 mL. The solution was spiked with *E. coli* from the daily working bacterial stock solution ($10^9 \text{ CFU}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$), leading to the desired initial bacterial concentration ($10^6 \text{ CFU}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$). The bacterial solution was mixed for 10 min, and then a sample was plated to measure the initial bacterial concentration ($t = 0$ min). A thermostated recirculation bath (Julabo F25, Germany) was used to maintain a constant temperature of the solution (20, 30, 40, and 50°C) while a magnetic stirrer bar was used to obtain a constant mixing speed of 350 rpm. Depending on the experiment, H_2O_2 from a $1000 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ stock solution was added into the system to a final concentration as 0, 5, 10, 30, and 50 ppm. For the experiments with bacterial debris as a sink for ROS, 15 min of boiling was performed to the corresponding *E. coli* concentration prior to spiking the water.

2.4. Analytical measurements

2.4.1. Bacterial enumeration

The spread plate method for bacteria quantification was applied using non-selective PCA growth medium, as previously reported [17], with a detection limit of $10 \text{ CFU}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ (1 colony in $100 \mu\text{L}$ sample). At pre-determined time intervals, 1 mL of sample was retrieved and analysed for its bacterial content. Aliquots were performed in sterile isotonic saline solution (0.8% NaCl/0.08% KCl) to achieve countable numbers on the 9-cm Petri dishes used. Every 10-fold dilution was

Table 1

Mechanisms of the cell's respiration pathways and bacterial inactivation routes by radical's damage and thermal effect. In bold: kinetic parameters estimated in this work.

R.1	$O_2^{\cdot -}$ generation during cell respiration	$O_2 + e^{-NADH} \rightarrow O_2^{\cdot -}$	$r_1 = k_1 [O_2][NADH] = k_1$	$k_1 = 5.4 \cdot 10^{-6} M^{-1} s^{-1}$ [26]
R.2	$O_2^{\cdot -}$ scavenging by SOD	$O_2^{\cdot -} + H^+ + SOD \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} H_2O_2 + \frac{1}{2} O_2$	$r_2 = k_2 [O_2^{\cdot -}][SOD]$	$k_2 = 10^9 M^{-1} s^{-1}$ [27]
R.3	H_2O_2 scavenging by CAT	$H_2O_2 + CAT \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} O_2 + H_2O$	$r_3 = k_3 [H_2O_2][CAT]$	$k_3 = 9 \cdot 10^5 M^{-1} s^{-1}$ [28]
R.4	Internal Fenton process	$Fe^{2+} + H_2O_2 \rightarrow Fe^{3+} + HO^- + HO$	$r_4 = k_4 [Fe^{2+}][H_2O_2]$	$k_4 (M^{-1} s^{-1})$
R.5	Internal Fenton-like process	$Fe^{3+} + Donor^{red} \rightarrow Fe^{2+} + Donor^{ox}$	$r_5 = k_5 [Fe^{3+}]$	$k_5 (s^{-1})$
R.6	Radical self-scavenging	$H_2O_2 + HO \rightarrow O_2^{\cdot -} + H_2O + H^+$	$r_6 = k_6 [H_2O_2][HO]$	$k_6 = 2.7 \cdot 10^7 M^{-1} s^{-1}$ [29]
R.7	$O_2^{\cdot -}$ disproportionation	$2O_2^{\cdot -} + 2H^+ \rightarrow H_2O_2 + O_2$	$r_7 = k_7 [O_2^{\cdot -}]^2$	$k_7 = 33.04 M^{-1} s^{-1}$ [30]
R.8	HO recombination	$2HO \rightarrow H_2O_2$	$r_8 = k_8 [HO]^2$	$k_8 = 4.6 \cdot 10^9 M^{-1} s^{-1}$ [31]
R.9	Bacterial damage mediated by $O_2^{\cdot -}$	$B_i + O_2^{\cdot -} \rightarrow B_{i+1}$	$r_9 = k_9 [O_2^{\cdot -}][B_i]$	$n = 27$ $k_9 (M^{-1} s^{-1})$
R.10	Bacterial damage mediated by HO	$B_i + HO \rightarrow B_{i+1}$	$r_{10} = k_{10} [HO][B_i]$	[32] $k_{10} (M^{-1} s^{-1})$
R.11	Thermal inactivation	$B_v \xrightarrow{T} B_{inactivated}$	$r_{11} = k_{11}(T)[B_v]$	$k_{R-ROS} = (s^{-1})$ $k_{011} (s^{-1}), E_{a11} (J \cdot mol^{-1})$

Table 2

Mechanism of the H_2O_2 decomposition and its consumption when added to water inoculated with *E. coli*. In bold: kinetic parameters estimated in this work.

R.A	H_2O_2 decomposition	$H_2O_{2,ext} \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} O_2 + H_2O$	$r_A = k_A [H_2O_{2,ext}]$	$k_A (s^{-1})$
R.B	H_2O_2 permeation	$H_2O_{2,ext} \rightarrow H_2O_2$	$r_B = k_B ([H_2O_{2,ext}] - [H_2O_2])$	$k_B = 70 s^{-1}$ [10]
R.C	Membrane- H_2O_2 interaction	$H_2O_{2,ext} + B_v \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} O_2 + H_2O + B_v$	$r_C = k_C [B_v][H_2O_{2,ext}]$	$k_C (M^{-1} s^{-1})$
R.D	MO killed cells- H_2O_2 interaction	$H_2O_{2,ext} + OM_{red} \rightarrow OM_{ox}$	$r_D = k_D [OM_{red}][H_2O_{2,ext}]$	$k_D (M^{-1} s^{-1})$

plated in duplicates, and at least two consecutive dilutions were plated for each experimental run.

2.4.2. H_2O_2 determination

The H_2O_2 concentration in solution was determined by the titanium oxysulfate method (DIN 38409–15). Briefly, 20 μ L of titanium oxysulfate was added in 1 mL of solution, forming a yellow complex of pertitanic acid. The absorbance of the mixture was measured using a UV-1800 spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan) at 410 nm.

3. Development of the mechanistic model

This section describes the mechanistic modelling of the H_2O_2 and thermal *E. coli* inactivation, including the assumptions, parameters and boundary conditions for the development of the kinetic model. The steps followed to model the *E. coli* inactivation kinetics induced by the addition of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) in the water matrix, under dark conditions at different temperatures were:

1. Bacteria: study of the cell's respiration pathways and thermal inactivation.
2. H_2O_2 : estimation of the H_2O_2 decomposition and its dependence on temperature.
3. Interaction between H_2O_2 and bacteria: study of H_2O_2 permeation into the cells, H_2O_2 interaction with the bacterial membrane, and with the organic matter derived from inactivated cells.

Following a mechanistic kinetic modelling approach based on the description of fundamental reactions and processes allows not only the interpolation, but also the extrapolation of the effects of the operational conditions, as well as the prediction of behaviours such as synergies. However, a rigorous description of the individual biochemical routes is beyond practical modelling applications. Mechanistic models capture the fundamental steps of the global process and are considered as an optimal compromise between the basic description of the process and the simplicity of the model's requirements for engineering objectives [5]. As a summary of the considered reactions, as defined by the assumptions 1–3 above, Table 1 and Table 2 present all the kinetic steps

considered in this model, namely Table 1: cellular respiration reactions, bacterial damage by radicals and thermal inactivation in dark conditions, and Table 2: external hydrogen peroxide behaviour: decomposition and interactions with the bacterial cells).

3.1. Bacterial metabolic pathways and thermal inactivation

Bacteria are complex microorganisms with several internal mechanisms to sustain their metabolic processes. Fairly often, radicals produced as by-products during the respiration process can adventitiously damage the cell. However, the bacteria count on enzymes and recovery mechanisms that control the concentration of these radicals and their damages, respectively, in order to avoid cell death. The whole process is in balance since all the mechanisms involved in cellular respiration are in steady-state. The essential reactions of this process are summarised in Table 1 and are explained in detail hereunder:

3.1.1. $O_2^{\cdot -}$ generation during cell respiration (R.1)

To generate energy, bacteria carry out cell respiration involving electron transport supplied by the redox cycle of the nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide enzyme ($NAD^+/NADH$). A small portion of free electrons interacts with the oxygen inside the cell to produce superoxide radicals ($O_2^{\cdot -}$) (R.1). The production of $O_2^{\cdot -}$ by this mechanism in aerobic metabolism was determined constant with a value of the kinetic constant $k_1 = 5-5.7 \cdot 10^{-6} M^{-1} s^{-1}$ [26].

3.1.2. $O_2^{\cdot -}$ scavenging by SOD (R.2)

Although the production of $O_2^{\cdot -}$ is constant, the levels of this radical during the metabolism remain low, around $10^{-10} M$, because the superoxide dismutase enzyme (SOD) reacts with it generating H_2O_2 [26]. Following the mechanism proposed by Castro-Alferez et al. [28], the reaction of $O_2^{\cdot -}$ and SOD can be defined as R.2. The kinetic constant of reaction can be assumed $k_2 = 10^9 M^{-1} s^{-1}$ [27]. The intracellular SOD concentration was found to be in the range $2-5 \cdot 10^{-4} M$ [33,34]. $2 \cdot 10^{-4} M$ was used in this work.

3.1.3. H_2O_2 scavenging by CAT (R.3)

The H_2O_2 produced during R.2 does not attack the cell by itself,

explaining the development of enzymes that convert O_2^- to H_2O_2 , a more preferred, less reactive ROS. However, H_2O_2 is still classified as a reactive oxygen species (ROS), which can easily generate other radicals that can potentially damage cell components directly; H_2O_2 levels as low as 10^{-6} M could be toxic for the cell [10]. The cell contains enzymes capable of decomposing H_2O_2 , maintaining its concentration around 10^{-9} M in steady-state and allowing the entire cellular recovery. Alkyl hydroperoxide reductase (Ahp) is the primary scavenger up to 10^{-5} M of H_2O_2 concentration. When levels of H_2O_2 are higher, the catalase enzyme (CAT) comes into play [9]. Furthermore, it has been proposed that when bacteria are suspended in H_2O_2 -rich water and/or water is illuminated by UV radiation, the internal H_2O_2 balance is interrupted, and the H_2O_2 concentration soars [10,28]. Since the amount of H_2O_2 is expected to be high, only the catalase (CAT) enzymes' action is considered. Following the simplified approach by Castro-Alferez et al. [28], the reaction can be expressed as R.3.

3.1.4. Internal Fenton process (R.4 and R.5)

Bacteria can induce the liberation of free iron to be a scavenger of H_2O_2 [35–37]. Growing *E. coli* cells contain approximately $2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M of free iron that is not integrated into proteins [35] or other structures. The presence of free iron and H_2O_2 makes possible the involvement of H_2O_2 in the Fenton process. The main reaction in the Fenton process is R.4, whose kinetic constant is usually reported as $76 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ (measured at pH 3 in a ferrous solution). However, this process is faster inside cells, where iron is present in the form of complexes that increase significantly Fenton kinetics. Park et al. measured the rate constant at physiological pH and in the presence of ATP and DNA included as iron ligands. The kinetic constant resulted in being strongly dependent on temperature, measuring $890 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ at 13°C and $4400 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ at 37°C [38]. The thermal dependence was modelled with an Arrhenius equation (eq. (1)):

$$k_4 = k_{04} \exp\left(\frac{-E_{a4}}{RT}\right) \quad (1)$$

where k_{04} is the preexponential constant, E_{a4} is the activation energy, and R is the ideal gas constant. The kinetic thermal parameters (k_{04} and E_{a4}) were estimated applying a lineal fitting to eq. (1) with both reported data from Park et al. [38].

The reduction of ferric iron to ferrous iron is usually driven by H_2O_2 . However, this reaction is too slow to regenerate sufficient Fe^{2+} to produce the observed DNA damage ($k = 2.7 \times 10^{-1} \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ [39]). In this sense, any cell donor donates more electrons that increase the kinetic rate of the reaction (R.5). To the best of our knowledge, no previous studies have reported the value of the kinetic constant for R.5 (k_5), being estimated in this work by means of the model regression.

3.1.5. ROS decomposition (R.6, R.7, and R.8)

As O_2^- , HO^\cdot radicals and H_2O_2 are highly reactive and not very selective, these species can react with each other involving a great number of by-products. This work considers the three more important reactions that take into account these three species: the reaction between HO^\cdot radical and H_2O_2 to produce O_2^- radicals (R.6) and the recombination of HO^\cdot and O_2^- radicals to generate H_2O_2 (R.7 and R.8, respectively). The second-order kinetic constant of the three reactions has been reported in the literature with values of $k_6 = 2.7 \cdot 10^7 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ [29], $k_7 = 3.3 \cdot 10^1 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ [30], and $k_8 = 4.6 \cdot 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ [31], values which we adopted for the intracellular environment. Some other substances also can damage the cell, such as hydroperoxyl radical (HO_2^\cdot) or singlet oxygen (1O_2). This approach does not consider these two species in order to make this mechanistic model less complex under fairly reasonable assumptions. For example, O_2^- and HO_2^\cdot exist in equilibrium in aqueous solution (pKa of $HO_2^\cdot = 4.88$), while about 0.3% of any superoxide in the protonated form is present in a physiological solution [40] so it can be neglected. Singlet oxygen, on the other hand, is predominantly a result

of photo-excitation or chemical processes not related to the physiological respiration pathways [37,41].

3.1.6. Bacterial damage (R.9 and R.10)

The intracellular generated O_2^- , and more importantly HO^\cdot , can non-selectively attack several cell targets. However, the inactivation is not instantaneous but occurs after the accumulation of a certain number of attacks. The series-event kinetic model [42] is able to reproduce this behaviour. This model assumes that an event is a unit of damage, and n units of damage must be accumulated to inactivate the microorganisms. Therefore, the inactivation process takes place through a sequence of inactivation levels (n) guided by a second-order kinetic constant (k_9 or k_{10}) with regard to the bacterial concentration for each level and the radical's concentration. Furthermore, bacteria have mechanisms which could repair damage caused by radical attacks to specific targets [43], e. g. protein misfolding chaperones, or DNA repair enzymes, inducing a step backwards in the level sequence. k_{R-ROS} was defined as a first-order kinetic constant of the sum of the recovery mechanisms with regards to the bacterial concentration at level i . Therefore, in the population balance of microorganisms at level i ($1 \leq i \leq n$), the damaged organisms from the previous level (B_{i-1}) and the recovered organisms from the next level (B_{i+1}) are considered as a source of organisms (positive term), and the damaged and recovered organisms at the current level (B_i) are considered as a sink of organisms (negative term). This balance is represented by eq. (2):

$$\frac{dB_i}{dt} = k_{9/10} \cdot I \cdot B_{i-1} \cdot OH \left/ O_2^- + k_{R-ROS} \cdot B_{i+1} - k_{9/10} \cdot I \cdot B_i \cdot OH \right/ O_2^- - k_{R-ROS} \cdot B_i \quad (2)$$

Casado et al. estimated $n = 27$ when they modelled the required number of levels of damage to inactivate an *E. coli* bacterium by HO^\cdot radicals since they consider the HO^\cdot radicals as the representative species of the radicals damage in the photo-Fenton process [32]. The same number of levels have been used for both reactions in this work, assuming that the bacteria can advance to the next level following an attack produced by O_2^- or by HO^\cdot radicals. k_9 and k_{10} , the kinetic constants of the damage reactions by both radicals (R.9 and R.10), as well as the kinetic constant of the regeneration step (k_{R-ROS}) were estimated by the model regression.

3.1.7. Thermal inactivation (R.11)

Cellular function in *E. coli* begins to be disrupted at 40°C because of the melting point of the lipid membranes, which involves a thermal inactivation [20,21]. Despite the fact that microorganisms are formed by different proteins and molecules, we can simplify the behaviour of the whole microorganism, and it can be approximated to one molecule [44,45]. Applying this assumption, the thermal inactivation can be easily modelled with R.11. The effect of the water temperature (T) on the thermal inactivation kinetic constant (k_{11}) was modelled by the Arrhenius equation (eq. (3)) where k_{011} is the temperature-independent pre-exponential factor, E_{a11} is the activation energy of the thermal reaction. Both parameters are unknown, and they are independently estimated in this work by experimental data.

$$k_{11} = k_{011} \exp\left(\frac{-E_{a11}}{RT}\right) \quad (3)$$

k_{011} and E_{a11} were independently estimated using experimental data of bacteria inactivation in the dark without H_2O_2 in the matrix water at different temperatures (20, 40, 45, and 50°C). Since bacterial concentration remains stable at $20\text{--}30^\circ\text{C}$, the observed bacteria die-off from 40°C and beyond was associated with the thermal inactivation. Therefore, the experimental data were fitted to a first-order kinetic model (R.11) to obtain the k_{11} constant for different temperatures. The same procedure was applied to estimate the Arrhenius parameters for the thermal bacterial inactivation (k_{011} and E_{a11}) with eq. (3) using the

data of k_{11} .

3.2. H_2O_2 decomposition and interactions

3.2.1. H_2O_2 decomposition (R.A):

Although the decomposition of H_2O_2 is very complex, it has been shown that under certain operating conditions, the kinetics of decomposition of H_2O_2 (R.A) can be described by a kinetic of pseudo first-order [22,23] (R.A) in which the kinetic constant (k_A) depends on the temperature (T) by the Arrhenius equation:

$$k_A = k_{0A} \exp\left(\frac{-E_{aA}}{RT}\right) \quad (4)$$

Where k_{0A} is the pre-exponential factor and E_{aA} the activation energy for the thermal H_2O_2 decomposition.

To study the thermal H_2O_2 decomposition in water, the concentration of H_2O_2 in water (without bacteria) was measured over time. This set of experiments was carried out at two initial H_2O_2 concentrations (10 ppm and 50 ppm) and at four temperatures (20, 30, 40, and 50 °C). Firstly, the k_A for each temperature level was calculated applying a linear fitting to R.A with the experimental data. The same procedure was applied to estimate the Arrhenius parameters for the thermal H_2O_2 decomposition (k_{0A} and E_{aA}) with eq. (4) using the previously obtained data of k_A .

3.2.2. H_2O_2 permeation into the cell (R.B)

Cells are permeable, thus, H_2O_2 can diffuse across the cell. If the external H_2O_2 concentration is higher than the internal one, this substance goes into the cell, increasing the internal H_2O_2 levels and disturbing the balance of the cellular mechanisms. The H_2O_2 influx depends on the diffusion constant (k_B), that is defined as:

$$k_B = P \cdot A / V_c \quad (5)$$

where P is the permeability coefficient of the bacteria, A is the membrane area, and V_c is the volume of a single bacterial cell. It has been estimated that $P = 1.6 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ cm} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, $A = 1.41 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^2$, and $V_c = 3.23 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^3$ in growing *E. coli* bacteria, resulting a $k_B = 70 \text{ s}^{-1}$ [10]. For simplicity, we considered the same values for the stationary phase cells in water.

3.2.3. H_2O_2 -cell membrane interaction (R.C)

H_2O_2 can interact with the cell membrane, specifically through lipids and amino acids, producing lesions on the cell [46]. Furthermore, the H_2O_2 concentration in water inoculated with *ompCF*-deficient *E. coli* decreased with time [18]. However, the interaction did not cause any inactivation of these porinless cells, most likely due to the cell's enzymatic defences, the aforementioned *E. coli* recovery mechanisms and consequently the limited reach of damage to critical targets. Although the interplay is not a source of damage for the bacteria, modelling this pathway is important since it disturbs the external H_2O_2 balance and, therefore, the internal H_2O_2 concentration. This reaction was expressed by a second-order kinetic model (R.C) where the kinetic constant (k_C) was estimated using reported data [18]. These data presented the H_2O_2 concentration profiles over time when porinless *E. coli* were exposed to two initial H_2O_2 concentrations (10 and 20 ppm). To describe this experiment, the second-order kinetic constant (R.C) becomes a pseudo first-order kinetic due to the constant *E. coli* concentration ($10^6 \text{ CFU} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$). In this sense, k_C was calculated applying a linear fitting to the eq. R.C with the experimental data. The resulting value of k_C should be normalised over the average number of reacting sites in a bacterium membrane in order to be compared to other second order kinetic such as radical-radical reactions [47].

3.2.4. H_2O_2 -oxidation targets from dead cells interaction (R.D)

In the same way that external H_2O_2 can react with the cell's

membrane, it also can react with oxidation targets that come from intracellular components or debris of dead cells. Cells can die due to high temperatures or the accumulation of attacks. In both cases, the lysis or the rupture of the membrane is expected, since temperature denatures constituents distributed in the membrane, and radicals can attack specific targets located in the membrane, as well as disturb the cell reparation mechanisms. As a result, the intracellular content is dispersed in the water matrix, being an H_2O_2 sink. This reaction was expressed with eq. (6) where one mol of external H_2O_2 reacts with a mol of oxidation targets.

$$r_D = k_D [H_2O_{2,ext}] [OM_{red}]; \quad (6)$$

This reaction resulted in being dependent on the temperature. Thus, the kinetic constant was defined with an Arrhenius equation as follows:

$$k_D = k_{0D} \exp\left(\frac{-E_{aD}}{RT}\right) \quad (7)$$

To estimate these kinetics parameters, a new set of experiments was performed: H_2O_2 at two different initial concentrations (10 and 50 ppm) was added to water at four different temperature levels (20, 30, 40, and 50 °C), inoculated with $10^6 \text{ CFU} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$ of previously boiled *E. coli* to remove the scavenger role of enzymes and induce the bacterial lysis. The evolution of the H_2O_2 concentration was measured, while organic matter and H_2O_2 balance were jointly solved to obtain the three unknown kinetic parameters of the reaction between the H_2O_2 and the organic matter coming from dead cells (ζ , k_{D0} , and E_{aD}). For the estimation of these parameters, the amount of organic matter provided by each dead bacterium was related to the term ($[B_{boiled}] = \zeta [OM_{red}]$) and the error between predicted and experimental H_2O_2 concentrations was minimised.

3.3. Estimation of kinetic parameters by model regression

k_4 , k_{011} , and E_{a11} were independently estimated, but it is not possible for k_5 , k_9 , k_{10} , and k_{R-ROS} since, to the best of our knowledge, there are not any data or procedures available to independently estimate them. Therefore, the assembled kinetic model was used to estimate the value of these parameters compared with a new set of experimental data. Since this kinetic model aims to predict bacterial inactivation in water with toxic levels of H_2O_2 at different temperatures, *E. coli* inactivation experiments with different concentrations of external H_2O_2 (0, 10, and 50 ppm) and at different temperatures (20, 30, 40, and 50 °C) were carried out. The *E. coli* and H_2O_2 concentration profiles over time were used to optimise the four variables, minimising the normal root mean square logarithmic error (NRMSLE) for bacteria profiles and the normalised root mean square error (NRMSE) for external H_2O_2 profiles between the experimental and the predicted data. The sequential quadratic programming (SQP) optimisation method from GNU Octave was used to minimise the objective error function. The system of differential equations was solved using explicit Euler. An independence analysis was carried out to achieve a low enough value for the time step.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Kinetic parameters

4.1.1. Iron oxidation during the intracellular Fenton process: k_4

k_4 literature values at different temperatures [38] were used to calculate Arrhenius parameters and get a temperature-dependent kinetic constant, resulting in $k_{04} = 8.21 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ M}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ and $E_{a4} = 4.9 \cdot 10^4 \text{ J} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$.

4.1.2. Thermal bacterial inactivation: k_{011} and E_{a11}

The results of each thermal inactivation experiment were fitted to a first-order decay trend. Those first-order constants (dots) and their

Fig. 1. First-order kinetic constants for bacterial thermal decomposition. Line: predicted data. Dots: experimental data (obtained in this work).

Fig. 3. H₂O₂ concentration profiles of *ompCF E. coli* mutants. Line: predicted data. Dots: experimental data (obtained from the literature [18]).

Fig. 2. First-order kinetic constants for H₂O₂ thermal decomposition. Line: predicted data. Dots: experimental data (obtained in this work).

fitting to Arrhenius law (line, $R^2 = 0.99$) are shown in Fig. 1. The Arrhenius fitting resulted in k_{011} as $4.18 \pm 0.04 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and Ea_{11} as $1.38 \pm 0.13 \cdot 10^5 \text{ J} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$.

4.1.3. H₂O₂ decomposition: k_A

The Arrhenius parameters for the thermal H₂O₂ decomposition were estimated as follows: k_{0A} as $394.7 \pm 112.5 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and Ea_A as $4.48 \pm 1.21 \cdot 10^4 \text{ J} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$. The fit between the observed and predicted values is shown in Fig. 2. Low values of kinetic constants (in the range between 7% and 25% reduction in 4 h) show the stability of H₂O₂ at room temperature and neutral pH.

4.1.4. H₂O₂-cell membrane interaction: k_C

Assuming a second-order kinetic equation to describe the interaction between the cell membrane and the external H₂O₂, the kinetic constant was estimated as $k_C = 2.04 \pm 0.16 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ($R^2 = 0.96$). The fit between the predicted results and the experimental data used [18] is shown in Fig. 3. k_C has a high value in a second order kinetic constant (higher than radical-radical reaction kinetics), but it must be considered

Fig. 4. H₂O₂ concentration profiles in the presence of boiled *E. coli* bacteria. Line: predicted data. Dots: experimental data (obtained in this work).

that before comparing the number should be normalised over the average number of reacting sites in the bacterial membrane [47].

4.1.5. H₂O₂-OM cell interaction: k_{D_0} , Ea_D , and ζ

The kinetic parameters described in Section 3.2.4 were estimated as follows: $k_{0D} = 2.14 \cdot 10^7 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $Ea_D = 4.93 \cdot 10^4 \text{ J} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$, and $\zeta = 3.63 \cdot 10^{11}$. As it was expected, the importance of dead cells in H₂O₂ kinetics is not insignificant; the value of the latter parameter means that just one dead cell provides an average of $3.63 \cdot 10^{11}$ oxidation targets to react with the external H₂O₂. These oxidation targets could be molecules that react once and/or molecules that produce reactive by-products. The excellent fit between the predicted and the experimental data (NRSME = 3.6%) is shown in Fig. 4.

4.1.6. Bacterial metabolic pathways: k_5, k_9, k_{10} , and k_{R-ROS}

The separate estimation of the kinetic parameters described in Section 3.3. led to the following values: $k_5 = 8.43 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_9 = 3.31 \cdot 10^1 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_{10} = 5.24 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k_{R-ROS} = 1.08 \cdot 10^1 \text{ s}^{-1}$ with an NRSME of 4.4 % (bacteria data) and an NRMSE of 12.9% (H₂O₂ data).

Fig. 5. Experimental and predicted concentration profiles. A) H_2O_2 concentration profiles with a 10^6 $CFU \cdot mL^{-1}$ initial concentration of viable *E. coli*. B) *E. coli* concentration profiles without H_2O_2 dissolved in the water matrix. C) *E. coli* concentration profiles with H_2O_2 dissolved in the water matrix. Line: predicted data. Dots: experimental data (obtained in this work).

Fig. 6. Experimental and predicted pseudo first-order kinetic constant of the *E. coli* inactivation with a 10^6 $CFU \cdot mL^{-1}$ initial concentration of viable *E. coli*.

Fitted curves are shown in Fig. 5A for the H_2O_2 and Fig. 5B and 5C for *E. coli* data. As it can be observed in Fig. 5B and 5C, the disinfection profiles have a linear shape. The series-event model is capable of developing profiles with curvilinear shape, being more curved for more events. However, in this case, the shape is linear due to the high value of the recovery constant (10.8 s^{-1}), which straightens the curve. In this sense, a pseudo first-order kinetic constant of each experiment has been obtained to compare with the equivalent experimental one. As a result, Fig. 6 showcases the great agreement between the experimental and predicted data of the bacterial disinfection.

The values calculated for k_9 and k_{10} may seem very low considering that they are second-order rate constants of radicals' reactions. The reason is that they are defined to account for the internal damages referenced to a single bacterial cell. Therefore, to compare these values with those usually reported in the literature for this type of reaction, it is necessary to change the units by multiplying them by the Avogadro's number and the cell volume. By doing so, these kinetic constants take the following values: $k'_9 = 2.35 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k'_{10} = 3.72 \cdot 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. It can be noticed that being R.10 a reaction with bacteria, the value of k'_{10} is significantly lower than the typical values of second-order reactions of hydroxyl radicals with chemicals.

The estimated values of the kinetic parameters agree with the *mode-one killing* cells by H_2O_2 , confirming that not only growing cells follow the two killing modes, but also stationary phase cells. For external H_2O_2 concentrations near 1–2 mM (approx. 34–68 ppm), bacteria are inactivated by the accumulation of DNA damage produced by radicals [12,24]. Fig. S1 shows the concentration profiles of internal cell species as Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , HO^\cdot , O_2^- , and H_2O_2 at different conditions of external H_2O_2 concentration and water temperature. In this Figure, it is observed that the amount of HO^\cdot varies significantly with experimental conditions and over time, while O_2^- concentration experiences small variations.

Another characteristic of the *mode-one killing* is a low value of the Fe^{2+} recycling rate. Although Fenton oxidation rate in cells is higher than usual ($k_4 = 4400 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 37°C [38]), if the cell's potential to reduce Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+} is also high, then the concentration of Fe^{2+} would be constant, and, therefore, the *mode-one killing* would not exist [24]. As it can be seen in Fig. S1, the concentrations of iron are dependent on the H_2O_2 concentration, varying from 0 to the total free iron concentration ($2 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ M}$). The obtained value for k_5 ($8.43 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) is low enough to guarantee the presence of Fe^{3+} under toxic levels of H_2O_2 and allows a decrease of Fe^{2+} concentration as the external H_2O_2 concentration rises (Fig. S1). Uhl et al. found this decrease necessary in the *mode-one killing* [24]. Indeed, for 50 ppm H_2O_2 concentration, all the iron appears in its

Fig. 7. *E. coli* inactivation rate of the different sinks for different experimental conditions (H_2O_2 concentration and water temperature). Y-axis shows the reaction rate divided by the bacterial concentration to present the effect of each variable.

ferric form, while for 0 ppm, it is shifted to ferrous form (Fig. S1). Regarding the donor substance that performs the ferric to ferrous iron reduction, some authors suggest that $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ or cysteine could be the reductant agent. During the oxidative process, the levels of $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ increase, raising the kinetic rate. However, $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ is excluded since k_5 would take a value around 10^{-5} s^{-1} (rate constant $10^5 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ [48] multiplied by the concentration 10^{-10} M (Fig. S1), and that would not suffice for the iron pool. So another suggestion is cysteine. Free cysteine is presented in low concentration to generate the strong DNA damage observed. It was previously found that when H_2O_2 is present, cysteine homeostasis is disrupted, and free cysteine storage increases around eightfold [49]. Therefore, cysteine could be the donor species, being in a concentration between 0.1 and 2 mM in the cell [49], which implies a more reasonable pathway, having a kinetic constant around $40\text{--}800 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Finally, this model also validates the fact reported by Seaver and Imlay: the action of the scavenging processes is quicker than the H_2O_2 permeation into the cell, hence the external H_2O_2 concentration is higher than the internal one (Fig. 4 and Fig. S1) [10].

4.2. *E. coli* inactivation

One of the advantages of applying the mechanistic models to the *E. coli* processes is the opportunity to understand the underlying mechanisms and the role of each substance, as well as to find reactions that do not play an important role, at least kinetically. In the next sections, the behaviour and the role of internal cell substances are studied, as well as the implications of the estimated values for the kinetic constants of the model are hereby developed.

The most probable causes of cell death were investigated for each experimental condition. As previously detailed, this kinetic model considers three different mechanisms that lead to *E. coli* inactivation: accumulation of n levels of damage produced by $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ (R.9) or by HO^{\cdot}

(R.10), or thermal inactivation (R.11). Fig. 7 shows the contribution of each *E. coli* inactivation pathway for 10 and 50 ppm addition of external H_2O_2 concentration and for 20, 40, and 50 °C. As it can be seen in Fig. 6, the experiments performed at temperatures below 40 °C showed a negligible thermal inactivation. All the experiments carried out at 0 ppm of external H_2O_2 (in which thermal inactivation is the unique cause of cell inactivation) showed the same negligible inactivation kinetic constant for temperatures below 40 °C. In addition, these results are in accordance with the literature. It has been reported that *E. coli* starts to present thermal denaturing around 40 °C [20,21]. For these reasons, data for temperatures in the 20–40 °C range are not included in this analysis.

As it can be observed for 50 °C experiments (Fig. 7), the main cell killing pathway is thermal inactivation. The inactivation rate is much higher than in experiments performed at lower temperatures, for all the external H_2O_2 concentrations studied. However, it is worth noting that for temperatures around 40 °C and 10 ppm H_2O_2 , the contribution of thermal and radical routes is almost equal. Finally, the unique path for inactivation at low temperatures (20 °C and 10 ppm H_2O_2) was the attack of radicals.

Even though the concentrations of $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ and HO^{\cdot} are in the same order of magnitude (Fig. S1), the reaction rate is much higher for the first one ($k_9 = 3.31 \cdot 10^1 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1} \gg k_{10} = 5.24 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$), meaning that the role of $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ is significant. This difference is reflected in all studied conditions. However, the role of HO^{\cdot} can be significant when water is illuminated with UV light since photo-Fenton can also happen inside the cell [19], and, in the present case, the results suggest it may be an essential radical in the cell death mechanism. The $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ has very important implications inside the cell. On one side, it can act as an important source of H_2O_2 (R.2), which in turn can fuel the Fenton process and lead to the generation of HO^{\cdot} . On the other hand, $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ is responsible for the degradation of iron-containing structures in the cell, such as the iron/sulfur clusters

Fig. 8. H_2O_2 consumption rates of the different sinks for different experimental conditions (H_2O_2 concentration and water temperature). Y-axis shows the reaction rate divided by the H_2O_2 concentration to present the effect of each variable.

[50], leading to the leaching of catalytically active Fe^{2+} , the second component of the Fenton process, as well as H_2O_2 generation [51]. This may explain the fact that although less thermodynamically favourable (-0.33 V), $\text{O}_2^{\cdot -}$ contribution is important compared to HO^{\cdot} (2.8 V). Furthermore, in stationary phase cells, the Dps (DNA Protection during Starvation) protein is effectively sequestering Fe and binds it to the DNA [52]. As a result, it utilises Fe^{2+} to react with H_2O_2 and protect the DNA from H_2O_2 damage [53] and other oxidative stress [54]. It is our suggestion that the presence of superoxide can lead to high Fe^{3+} reduction to Fe^{2+} and high catalytically active iron liberation near the DNA, which may be damaged by the HO^{\cdot} radicals generated. The latter process justifies its high importance in the inactivation process.

4.3. H_2O_2 sinks

As the kinetic model reflects (Fig. 8), the consumption of the external H_2O_2 is highly related to the number of viable cells that remains in the water. For example, at 20 °C, the bacteria's death happens progressively by the radicals' damage. In this sense, the primary H_2O_2 sinks are cell permeation and membrane reactions. Instead, at 50 °C, the number of viable cells plummeted due to the thermal inactivation, preventing a noticeable permeation or membrane interaction, but leading to the generation of increasing concentrations of organic matter. Furthermore, the reaction of organic matter with H_2O_2 is also noticeably depending on temperature. In addition, the H_2O_2 thermal decomposition is not still very significant at 50 °C. Thus, the major H_2O_2 sink at high temperatures is the interaction with the bacterial matter.

5. Conclusions

This work presents for the first time a kinetic model that considers thermal, external, and internal mechanisms that constitute the *mode-one killing* of *E. coli* inactivation with H_2O_2 . The development of a

mechanistic model allows determining the inactivation routes and the role played by each involved mechanism. Some new conclusions have been obtained from the development of this kinetic model. More specifically, we have concluded that at low water temperature (20–35 °C), the inactivation is led by radicals' damage, and it is demonstrated that the role of the $\text{O}_2^{\cdot -}$ in cell inactivation is significant. In addition, externally added H_2O_2 is mainly consumed by the interaction with the cell's membrane and during/after its permeation. However, at 40 °C, the contribution of the radicals' damage and the thermal on the bacteria inactivation is comparable. On the other hand, at higher water temperatures (50 °C), the inactivation is faster and strongly controlled by thermal inactivation, suggesting that even at high H_2O_2 concentrations, this pathway remains unchanged. Furthermore, we have made new strides in attributing a competing role to dead cells in the medium. Cell components and remaining debris are the main sinks of ineffective consumption of the externally added H_2O_2 . Last but not least, our work has led to suggest updated and corrected values for the kinetic parameters of the internal Fenton process under external H_2O_2 addition.

Beyond its contribution to elucidating the complex mechanisms occurring inside the cell, this work lays a solid foundation for further modelling different inactivation mechanisms. One of the strengths of mechanistic modelling is its coherence, both under quantitative changes in experimental conditions and under qualitative changes in the experiments, such as the addition of new inactivation agents. Its modular character will allow, in Part 2 of this work, to focus on solar disinfection enhanced by toxic levels of external addition of H_2O_2 , including the mechanisms of the dark phenomena studied in this part.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.135709>.

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